

Effect of Neuromodulation on the Brain Dynamical Repertoire

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Abstract. Brain dynamics go beyond simple bistable models of regional activation, encompassing multiple coexisting states and transitions. Neural activity is constrained to low-dimensional manifolds, where structured flow governs brain function. Neuromodulators such as dopamine, serotonin, and acetylcholine shape this landscape by modulating synaptic plasticity, neuronal excitability, and network connectivity. Here, we investigate how neuromodulation alters neural dynamics. Using a neural mass model incorporating dopamine, we show that increasing dopaminergic input expands the repertoire of dynamical patterns and shifts their frequency content. These findings underscore the critical role of neuromodulation in shaping brain states and highlight the importance of computational models that integrate these effects to better understand both healthy and pathological brain dynamics.

Keywords: Brain dynamics · Neuromodulation · Dopamine

Brain dynamics refers to the complex patterns of neural activity that underlie cognition, perception, and behavior, which can be modeled using mathematical and computational frameworks [26, 11, 14, 12] to understand transitions between different healthy or pathological brain states [11, 15]. Often, theoretical models of neural activity have focused on bistable regimes to explain key cognitive and behavioral functions, such as decision-making, working memory, motor control or healthy and pathological states [42, 19, 30]. However, accumulating evidence suggests that neural circuits often support a richer dynamical repertoire, including multistability and complex attractor landscapes [5].

One key regulator of these dynamic states is the neuron’s neurochemical environment, which includes ionic dynamics, local protein expression, and neuromodulatory input. Neuromodulators such as dopamine, serotonin, acetylcholine, and noradrenaline play a crucial role in shaping the stability and flexibility of neural activity by influencing synaptic plasticity, neuronal excitability, and network connectivity. The evolutionary changes of these modulatory systems have likely contributed to the brain’s capacity for adaptive cognition, allowing for transitions between multiple functional states [7].

Considering neuromodulation in computational models becomes necessary to capture a more complete brain dynamical repertoire. By exploring how neuromodulatory influences extend the dynamical possibilities of neural networks, we can explore and better understand some of the mechanisms underlying cognitive flexibility, consciousness, and pathological states such as schizophrenia, depression, and Parkinson’s disease [10, 29, 9, 2].

The brain is a high-dimensional dynamical system, continuously processing information through complex interactions between neurons and brain regions. Neural activity evolves over time, shaping perception, cognition, and motor control. Despite the vast number of neurons, brain dynamics do not explore the entire high-dimensional space of possible neural states. Instead, neural activity is constrained to lower-dimensional structures, reflecting coordinated patterns of activation.

This organization emerges from the connectivity and functional architecture of neural circuits. Experimental studies reveal that population activity often resides on low-dimensional manifolds, and that neural states evolve along structured trajectories rather than arbitrarily fluctuating (see for example [33, 32, 31]). These manifolds define the intrinsic space of computation, where neural trajectories encode cognitive processes, sensorimotor transformations, and learning.

Mathematically, the time evolution of neural states can be described as a structured flow on a manifold [27], where a set of variables governs the system’s dynamics.

In this work, we give a brief conceptual introduction to the structured flows on manifolds framework for brain dynamics and the influence of neuromodulation. Then we propose an applied example with a neural mass model taking into account dopamine dynamics. We show how different levels of dopamine lead to different numbers of patterns in the dynamical repertoire, and changes in their features, such as frequency content.

1 Landscape of brain dynamics

In brain dynamics, structured flow on a manifold describes the organized evolution of neural activity within a constrained space of possible brain states (Fig. 1A). A manifold represents the low-dimensional structure underlying high-dimensional neural activity, where neurons or brain regions interact in a way that restricts possible neural states to specific trajectories. Rather than exploring all configurations randomly on the manifold, neural activity follows a structured flow, determined by intrinsic neural dynamics, anatomical connectivity, external stimuli, and cognitive tasks. This flow is shaped by the landscape of attractors (e.g., stable fixed points and limit cycles or chaotic attractors) and repellers (e.g., unstable fixed-points or unstable limit-cycles). For example, in the motor cortex, neural activity follows low-dimensional trajectories during movement execution [1]. This framework is relevant to sensorimotor control [24], but also in resting state activity [18] and pathological dynamics such as observed in epilepsy during seizures [35], thus offering a conceptual framework to study brain dy-

namics [27]. Empirically, structured flow on neural manifolds can be identified using dimensionality reduction techniques such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Gaussian Process Factor Analysis (GPFA), t-SNE, UMAP, or Laplacian Eigenmaps [6, 22, 37, 25, 16, 3]. These methods help extract the intrinsic manifold structure and reveal how neural states evolve in a constrained manner [36, 35, 18]. Moreover, recently developed methods such as neural ODE [8], have the potential to help in reconstructing the flow on the manifold. The state of neural activity at a given time can be represented as a high-dimensional vector:

$$\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^N \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of neurons or brain regions, depending on the scale of interest. However, neural activity often evolves following a structured flow on a lower-dimensional manifold $\mathcal{M} \subset \mathbb{R}^N$, meaning that neural states follow structured trajectories instead of freely exploring all possible states. If the intrinsic dimensionality of the manifold is d , we can describe the neural state as:

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \Phi(\mathbf{z}(t)), \quad \mathbf{z}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^d \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{z}(t)$ represents latent coordinates on the manifold \mathcal{M} , and $\Phi : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N$ is the embedding function. The temporal evolution of neural states follows a dynamical system:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{x}}{dt} = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})$ is a vector field that governs the flow of neural activity. Since neural states are restricted to \mathcal{M} , we express the dynamics in terms of the variables:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{z}}{dt} = \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{z}) \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{z})$ describes the intrinsic flow of neural activity within the manifold. Neural systems often exhibit attractor dynamics, where brain states converge toward stable points or recurrent patterns. Fixed points of the system satisfy:

$$\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{z}^*) = 0 \quad (5)$$

However, in higher-dimensional systems, more complex types of attractors emerge beyond simple fixed points. In two-dimensional ($d = 2$) neural manifolds, the system can support limit cycles, where activity does not settle at a single stable point but instead follows a periodic trajectory. Limit cycles often characterize rhythmic neural processes such as oscillations in motor control, central pattern generators, and cortical rhythms [34, 28, 26].

As the dimensionality increases ($d \geq 3$), neural systems can give rise to chaotic attractors, where trajectories remain bounded but exhibit sensitive dependence on initial conditions. This behavior is typical in high-dimensional cortical networks, where chaotic activity enables flexibility and computational richness [4, 17].

The dimensionality of the manifold thus contributes to the richness of attractor structures, with neural circuits exploiting these properties to maintain flexible yet stable computational states [21].

Attractors in a dynamical system encode the long-term stable behavior of the system. This dynamics can be intuitively understood using a ball-on-a-landscape analogy: if a ball is placed on an uneven surface, it will roll downhill due to gravity, eventually coming to rest at the lowest point of a valley, corresponding to an attractor (Fig. 1B), and moving back towards it after small perturbations. As mentioned above, attractors are not limited to fixed points, that is solutions at fixed values of the variables as at the bottom of the valleys of the landscape, but include periodic solutions or chaotic attractors. We thus use the landscape analogy as a conceptual simplification, keeping in mind that the valleys can host more complex behaviors.

The system will set into a different attractor depending on its initial conditions and stronger perturbations can push it from one attractor to the other.

Neuromodulators such as acetylcholine, dopamine, serotonin, and norepinephrine modify the attractor landscape by reshaping the existence, type, stability, depth, and separability of attractors in the neural dynamical system. This modulation influences how neural activity evolves and the repertoire of possible states, as shown in Fig. 1B.

2 Neuromodulation (re) shapes the landscape

As a concrete example, we use a neural mass model derived from mean-field theory, which represents the average activity of a spiking neural network [13]. This model includes the influence of dopaminergic input received by the neural population. Such models have been used to create whole-brain simulations, including virtual models of Parkinsonian patients, to estimate dopamine levels [2]. In this study, we focus on a single population of neurons, whose activity is governed by Equations 6.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} r(t) = 2arv + br - (A_{Dp}[D_p] + B_{Dp})g_a S_a r - g_g S_g r + \frac{a\Delta}{\pi} \\ v(t) = av^2 + bv + c + \eta - \frac{\pi^2 r^2}{a} \\ \quad + (A_{Dp}[D_p] + B_{Dp})g_a S_a (E_a - V) + g_g S_g (E_g - V) - u + I_{ext} \\ u(t) = \alpha(\beta V - u) + u_d r \\ S_a(t) = \frac{-S_a}{\tau_{S_a}} + S_{ja} c_{exc} + J_a r \\ S_g(t) = \frac{-S_g}{\tau_{S_g}} + S_{jg} c_{inh} \\ \tau_{Dp}[D_p(t)] = k c_{dopa} - \frac{V_{max}[D_p]}{(K_m + [D_p])} \end{array} \right. \quad (6)$$

In this system of equations, the variables are: r is the firing rate of the neuron group, v is the average membrane potential, u is an adaptation parameter that reflects differences between cell types, s_a is the average excitatory AMPA synaptic activity, s_g is the average inhibitory GABA synaptic activity, $[D_p]$ is

Fig. 1. Neuromodulation alters the Structured Flow on Manifold - **A.** Neural activity doesn't explore the full high-dimensional neural space \mathbf{x} , but rather evolves on a lower-dimensional manifold, spanned by local variables \mathbf{z} that evolve in a structured way according to some dynamics $\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{z})$. Trajectories (in blue) rapidly collapse on the manifold, on which the flow occurs on slower timescales. **B.** Cartoon of a landscape to exemplify how the flow constraints trajectories. The system (here, the ball) eventually reaches an attractor (here, the bottom of a valley) depending on its initial conditions. Attractors can be simple fixed values dynamics (fixed points), but also oscillatory (limit cycles) or even chaotic ones (chaotic attractors). Neuromodulation alters the flow, modifying the attractors landscape and thus the system behavior.

the local concentration of dopamine, and M is the modulation caused by the activation of dopamine receptors.

Parameters details, identified in previous works [39, 2, 13], are given in Table 1. This neural mass model typically represents one neuronal population receiving excitatory input from other brain regions through the excitatory coupling c_{exc} , and inputs from inhibitory populations through c_{inh} . We study the dynamical regime emerging for constant inhibitory and excitatory inputs for different levels of dopamine received through c_{dopa} . Different dynamical patterns have been identified in this model, namely, bursting, fixed-point, and limit-cycle oscillation (see Fig. 2A). We analyzed the types of dynamical patterns that emerge under different levels of inhibitory and excitatory constant inputs (see Fig. 2B). As the level of incoming dopaminergic input varied, the system's dynamical repertoire changed, increasing from two patterns (Fig. 2B, first and last column) to four patterns (Fig. 2B, third column).

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Parameter	Symbol	Value
QIF parameter	a	0.04	Adaptation step	u_d	12
QIF parameter	b	5	Time constant of AMPA synapses	τ_{S_a}	5
QIF parameter	c	140	Time constant of GABA synapses	τ_{S_g}	5
Adaptation parameter	α	0.013	Time constant of dopamine concentration	τ_{D_p}	500
Adaptation parameter	β	0.4	Strength of AMPA synapses	$S_{j,a}$	0.008
Mean additive current	η	18	Strength of GABA synapses	$S_{j,g}$	0.008
Maximal conductance of AMPA	g_a	12	Maximum dopamine reuptake rate	V_{max}	1300
Maximal conductance of GABA	g_g	12	Michaelis constant	K_m	150
Additive current half-width distribution	Δ	1	Dopamine coupling factor	k	1000
Dopamine linearization factor	A_{D_p}	1	Basal level (no neuromodulation)	B	0.2
Reversal potential of AMPA synapses	E_a	0	External current	I_{ext}	0
Reversal potential of GABA synapses	E_g	-80			

Table 1. Neural mass model parameter values

Fig. 2. Neural Mass Model's repertoire evolves with c_{dopa} - **A**. This Neural Mass Model can display distinct paths of activity: Bursting (B), defined by bursts of fast spiking activity separated by quiescent intervals; Fixed Point (FP) in which the dynamics converges towards a constant stable value; Limit Cycle (LC) characterized by sustained spiking activity. **B**. Changes in the dopaminergic input induce variations in the neural mass model behavior as depicted in the first row, where is highlighted how, maintaining the same range of values for the external inputs c_{exc} and c_{inh} , distinct dynamical regimes can emerge as the level of c_{dopa} is increased. Moreover, a quantitative modification in the dynamics of the model is also observed. In particular, it is evinced how, by gradually increasing c_{dopa} , the region in which the system displays "silent" behavior, characterized by a low mean value of the firing rate, becomes dominant and the frequencies of oscillations (both fast and inter-burst) simultaneously decrease.

3 Discussion

Neuromodulators act as control parameters that reshape the geometry, the topology and stabilities of the brain's dynamical landscape, playing an influential role in cognitive flexibility, learning, attention, and decision-making.

The brain's computational capabilities, information storage, and integrative processing are fundamentally influenced by the number and structure of

its attractors. In dynamical systems theory, attractors correspond to stable or metastable states of neural activity, each defining a distinct computational basin. A richer attractor repertoire expands the discrete state space available for encoding information, enhancing both representational complexity and processing flexibility. Each attractor represents a reproducible neural configuration. For example it allows the system to map external inputs to distinct memory states. This is particularly evident in recurrent cortical networks, where attractor dynamics shape neural activity and serve as a fundamental mechanism for working memory. [23, 43, 41]. In the prefrontal cortex, for example, persistent attractors maintain transiently stored information through stable firing patterns, modulated by synaptic and intrinsic neuronal mechanisms. Similarly, in the hippocampus, attractors underpin spatial memory, with place cells exhibiting activity patterns corresponding to distinct locations. The richness of the attractor landscape determines the encoding capacity for spatial environments, influencing navigational and episodic memory precision. More generally, a higher-dimensional dynamical system, characterized by a richer attractor set, enhances the brain’s ability to differentiate input patterns, increasing encoding specificity and reducing representational ambiguity.

Beyond information storage, attractor richness plays a crucial role in determining computational power and functional complexity. Neural computation relies on nonlinear transformations, where the ability to transition between attractors enables higher-order information integration and flexible cognitive processing [20]. The brain is thought to operate near a critical point between order, where a limited number of attractors restricts flexibility, and chaos, where excessive attractor richness leads to instability. This criticality maximizes computational efficiency by optimizing information transfer, dynamic range, and responsiveness to perturbations. In this regime, the system exhibits scale-free dynamics, ensuring an optimal trade-off between stability and flexibility [40]. Furthermore, the hierarchical organization of neural systems, where local circuits function within broader regional or global attractor landscapes, supports multi-scale processing. Early sensory areas encode fine-grained features within low-dimensional attractors, while higher-order cortical regions integrate these representations across broader attractor manifolds. This structured yet flexible attractor space enables efficient information processing, robust cognition, and adaptive behavior across multiple scales.

These dynamical processes evolve with the aging brain, where the variation in concentrations of neuromodulators, such as acetylcholine, dopamine, and norepinephrine, affects memory and cognitive capabilities [38]. This framework explains why neuromodulatory dysfunction is linked to psychiatric and neurological disorders, where pathological shifts in manifold structure lead to rigidity (e.g., Parkinson’s disease), instability (e.g., schizophrenia), or maladaptive exploration (e.g., ADHD).

Acknowledgments. The preparation of this article was funded through the EU’s Horizon Europe Programme under the Specific Grant Agreement No. 101147319 (EBRAINS 2.0), and from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme under the Specific Grant Agreement No. 101137289 (Virtual Brain Twin Project). The project leading to this publication has also received funding from the Excellence Initiative of Aix-Marseille Université - AMidex, a French “Investissements d’Avenir programme” AMX-21-IET-017. The authors acknowledge support from the grant "Personalised brain models of Parkinson’s disease patients". (*"Modèle de cerveau personnalisé pour les patients atteints de la maladie de Parkinson"*). Lithuanian-French programme Gilibert, project No 2024-PRO-00148/ P-LZ-24-6, 2025-2026.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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